

Frontiers of Transdisciplinary Knowledge Management in Digital Humanities

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Abstract:

The 4th Industrial Revolution, or 2nd digital revolution, has brought about drastic changes in the economy and society, as technology develops at a rapid pace. Digital humanities take advantage of this technological evolution to uncover new ways to approach the humanities and the social sciences. In particular, the 4IR has enabled the development of new technologies that are facilitating the integration of virtual and physical environments in different digital humanities sectors, such as arts and culture. In addition, it helped digital humanities scholars to analyse massive amounts of data and apply machine learning algorithms to identify patterns, uncover new insights and approach cultural, historical, and literary phenomena in

a more comprehensive and differentiated way. In the context of 4IR, the Semantic Web plays a crucial role in enabling machines and humans to access and use the vast amount of data generated by advanced technologies, by providing a common language and structure for data exchange and integration.

Keywords: *digital humanities, semantic Web, 4IR.*

Introduction

The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) is the current phase of industrial development characterized by the integration of advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, robotics, and block chain, into various industries (Schwab, 2016). This integration aims to enhance efficiency, productivity, and innovation in industries (Anshari et al., 2022).

On the other hand, the Semantic Web is a vision of the World Wide Web where the content is machine-readable and understandable by computers, enabling them to process and use the information in a more intelligent and efficient way. Relying on a set of standards and

technologies, including Resource Description Framework (RDF), Web Ontology Language (OWL), and SPARQL query language, it aims to create a web of linked data that can be easily shared, reused, and combined by various applications and services (Sorbara, 2020).

Digital humanities are an interdisciplinary field that combines traditional humanities disciplines with computational methods and digital technologies to study human culture and society. It includes a wide range of activities, such as text mining, data visualization, network analysis, and digital archiving. Digital humanities scholars use these methods to analyse and interpret cultural and social data, explore new research questions, and generate insights that would not be possible using traditional methods alone.

It is a rapidly evolving field that has been driven by advances in digital technology and the growth of digital data, it has had a significant impact on fields such as literature, history, archaeology, anthropology, and cultural studies, and has enabled new forms of interdisciplinary research and collaboration. Finally, has also helped to democratize access to cultural and historical information, making it more widely available to scholars, students, and the general public.

Digital humanities, the semantic web, and the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) are all interconnected through the use of technology to improve humanities research and advance the development of the humanities.

Digital Humanities on the Semantic Web

By leveraging the technology of the semantic web, digital humanities scholars can create linked data sets that allow for more complex and sophisticated analysis of cultural and historical phenomena. For example, they can create ontologies that define relationships between concepts and entities, and use these ontologies to build linked data sets that can be analysed using data mining and visualization tools. They can also use natural language processing tools to extract meaning from textual data and create annotations that provide additional context and interpretation.

In addition, the semantic web enables digital humanities projects to be more collaborative and interdisciplinary, as it provides a common framework for organizing and sharing data across different disciplines and research domains. This allows researchers from different fields to work together more effectively and to combine their expertise to create more comprehensive and nuanced interpretations of cultural, historical, and literary phenomena. Some examples of new technologies that are being used in digital humanities on the semantic web are presented below.

Natural language processing (NLP)

1. NLP is a field of computer science and artificial intelligence that focuses on enabling computers to interpret and understand human language. It involves the use of machine learning algorithms to analyse and understand human language (Jurafsky & Martin, 2020). In digital humanities it is used to analyse text data, enabling researchers to identify patterns and trends in large-scale data sets. Some examples of NLP techniques that are commonly used in digital humanities research include:

2. Named Entity Recognition (NER), which involves identifying and categorizing named entities, such as people, places, and organizations, in text data. In DH research, it enables researchers to identify key figures and locations in historical and cultural texts.

3. Sentiment Analysis, which is a method to analyse text data and determine the emotional tone or sentiment of the text and it helps DH researchers analyse how people felt about certain cultural and historical events or figures (Liu, 2012)

4. Topic Modeling, a technique that involves identifying topics or themes in text data and can be used to analyse the themes and topics that are present in cultural and historical texts (Blei, 2012).

5. Text Classification, that classifies and organizes large-scale text data sets based on its content.

Linked data (LD)

Linked data is a method of publishing structured data on the web, that enables machines to interpret and link together data from different sources. The fundamental difference between the traditional Web and the Semantic Web is that while the Web is constructed of interlinked documents (such as web pages), the Semantic Web is based on the linkage of semantically defined data called Linked Data. Linked Data is not a specific technology or tool, but rather a set of guidelines for publishing structured data that support the development of interoperable machine-readable data on the Semantic Web.

A survey from Hawkins (2022), indicated that the utilization of Linked Data is a promising approach to enhancing the accessibility of digitized and born-digital archives, resulting in the creation of enriched, interoperable, and integrated large-scale archival datasets that can be utilized in various ways (Hawkins, 2022). Presently, the primary focus of Archival Linked Data endeavours is the publication of archival metadata as Linked Data. Nevertheless, it is the contents of born-digital and digitized records that hold the most potential for researchers, making it imperative for archive services to transform their collections into data. There is a shared appreciation and desire for access to archives in digital forms and as data, indicating that collaboration with digital humanists would be mutually beneficial for both the archives sector and Digital Humanities. By advocating for Archival Linked Data and demonstrating its benefits to archive users, digital humanists can serve as an essential ally and help ensure that it continues to be a valuable tool.

Spatial analysis (SA)

Spatial analysis involves the use of geographic information systems (GIS) and other tools to study, measure and analyse the spatial distribution and relationships of geographic features or objects (Chen et al., 2019). It is used in various fields, including urban planning, environmental management, public health, criminology, and natural resource management and can be applied to address a wide range of research questions, such as understanding the spatial patterns of diseases, analysing land-use changes, mapping crime hotspots, and identifying environmental risks.

Some common applications of spatial analysis include creating maps and visualizations, performing spatial interpolation and extrapolation, conducting network analysis, and modelling spatial processes. By analysing data in a spatial context, researchers can gain valuable insights into the relationships and patterns that exist within a given location, which can inform decision-making and policy development. In digital humanities research field, it can be used

to analyse the spatial distribution of cultural and historical phenomena.

Data visualization

Data visualization involves the use of visual representations, such as graphs and maps, to communicate complex data sets. Data visualization tools can aid in the analysis and communication of complex information in digital humanities research. Some popular tools for data visualization in digital humanities include:

1. Tableau: a powerful data visualization software that allows users to create interactive dashboards, charts, and graphs with easy-to-use drag-and-drop functionality.
2. Gephi: an open-source software for visualizing and exploring complex networks and graphs, which can be used to analyse social networks, historical networks, and literary networks.
3. Palladio: a web-based tool for exploring and visualizing complex data, which enables users to create interactive maps, timelines, and network graphs.
4. Voyant Tools: a suite of web-based tools for text analysis and visualization, which allows users to explore and visualize large sets of text data.
5. RAW Graphs: an open-source data visualization tool that can be used to create a variety of visualizations, including scatter plots, tree maps, and sankey diagrams.
6. D3.js: a powerful JavaScript library for creating interactive and customizable visualizations, which allows users to create a wide range of visualizations, including charts, maps, and diagrams.

Machine learning

Machine learning involves the use of algorithms to identify patterns in data and make predictions. The technologies and tools that are used for machine learning, such as Natural Language

Toolkit, Mallet, OpenCV, WEKA etc., can offer multiple possibilities for the researchers, to analyse large and complex data sets. Moreover, Python offers several libraries such as Scikit-Learn, TensorFlow, and PyTorch that provide machine learning algorithms.

The Sampo model and the Portal series

The Sampo model and the Portal series are two well-known digital humanities projects based on Semantic Web (Hyvönen, 2022). The Sampo Model is a framework for creating semantic portals that provide access to structured data related to cultural heritage and other topics of interest to the humanities.

It consists of three layers: the conceptual, the contextual, and the data layer. The first one defines the concepts and relationships between cultural heritage objects, while the second one provides information about the cultural, historical, and social context of these objects. The data layer, finally, consists of the actual data about cultural heritage objects, which is organized and made accessible through the semantic infrastructure.

One of the key advantages of the Sampo Model is that it provides a flexible and extensible framework for representing cultural heritage data. This means that it can be used to represent a wide range of cultural heritage objects, from simple objects like images and documents to more complex objects like archaeological artefacts and historical buildings. It has already been applied to a number of different cultural heritage domains, including Finnish cultural heritage, Byzantine heritage, and maritime heritage, in order to create a linked data infrastructure that makes it possible to analyse and understand cultural heritage objects in new and innovative ways.

Table 1. A Selection of Sampo Portals

Portal	Description
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Sampo-UI	A user interface for exploring and browsing large, heterogeneous data collections.
Sampo Model Core	A web-based application for modelling data in the humanities and social sciences, used to build the other Sampo portals.
Finnish People	A portal for exploring biographical data on historical Finnish people, including information on their occupations and social networks.
BiographySampo	A portal for exploring biographical data, including information on individuals' life events, relationships, and careers.
BookSampo	A portal for exploring digitized books, including their contents, metadata, and contextual information.
WarSampo	A portal for exploring data related to the Second World War in Finland, including military operations, battles, and air raids.
KulturSampo	A portal for exploring cultural heritage data in Finland, including artworks, photographs, and historical buildings.

Besides the many advantages, Sampo Model, has been criticized for being a complex tool that requires significant technical expertise to use effectively, and this may limit its accessibility to researchers with limited technical skills or resources (Borg et al., 2017). The accuracy and completeness of the data used to build the Sampo Model have been also called into question, as the model relies on multiple datasets that may have different standards for data quality (Passarotti et al., 2018). Finally, some researchers have noted that the Sampo Model is not always transparent in how it processes and analyses

data, which can make it difficult for other researchers to reproduce results or verify the accuracy of its analyses (Garcia-Suarez et al., 2018).

The Portal Series, on the other hand, is a collection of individual portals that have been developed using the Sampo Model, each focused on a specific topic or area of inquiry (Chen et al., 2019). The series includes three main tools: Text Encoding Initiative (TEI), TokenX, and CollateX. While the series has been praised for its ability to enhance textual analysis and interpretation, there have also been criticisms regarding its limitations and complexity.

One of the main benefits of the Portal Series is its use of the TEI standard for encoding textual data. This standard allows researchers to mark-up text with specific tags and attributes that provide information about the structure, meaning, and context of the text. This, in turn, enables researchers to perform a range of analyses on the text, including text mining, visualization, and computational analysis.

Another benefit, is its ability to work with large and complex textual datasets. TokenX, for example, can automatically segment texts into meaningful units and assign them a range of linguistic attributes, such as parts of speech and named entities. CollateX, on the other hand, can compare different versions of the same text and identify similarities and differences between them.

However, there have been criticisms of the Portal Series, particularly regarding its complexity and learning curve (Archer, 2018). Some researchers have found the tools to be difficult to use, particularly for those who are not well-versed in programming and mark-up languages. Additionally, the tools have been criticized for their lack of integration with other software tools, which can make it challenging to use them in conjunction with other digital humanities workflows (Hartsell-Gundy et al., 2015).

Another criticism of the Portal Series is that it can be time-consuming to encode and process textual data using these tools (Arnold & Tilton,

2015; Ye et al., 2017). While they offer powerful functionalities, they require a significant investment of time and effort to learn and apply effectively. This can be a barrier to entry for some researchers, particularly those who may have limited resources or time to invest in learning new tools.

Recommendations for further research

Further research could explore the ways in which digital humanities can continue to advance using technologies like natural language processing, linked data, and spatial analysis. One potential area of research could be how digital humanities can be used to make cultural and historical information more accessible to a broader audience, including people from different backgrounds and cultures. By democratizing access to such information, digital humanities can help address issues of inclusivity and diversity in humanities research.

Another area of research could be the ethical and social implications of using advanced technologies in humanities research. As technologies become more advanced, the potential impact on society as a whole must be considered. For example, the use of natural language processing and linked data could raise questions about privacy and data protection, while the use of spatial analysis could raise issues around the representation and interpretation of data.

In conclusion, further research is needed to explore the ways in which digital humanities can advance, democratize access to information, address issues of inclusivity and diversity, and consider the ethical and social implications of using advanced technologies in humanities research. This research can help shape the future of digital humanities and ensure that it continues to be a field that benefits society as a whole.

Conclusion

The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), the Semantic Web, and Digital Humanities are all interconnected through the use of technology to improve humanities research and advance the development of the humanities. By leveraging the technology of the Semantic Web, digital humanities scholars can create linked data sets that allow for more complex and sophisticated analysis of cultural and historical phenomena.

The Semantic Web also enables digital humanities projects to be more collaborative and interdisciplinary, as it provides a common framework for organizing and sharing data across different disciplines and research domains. NLP, Linked Data, and Spatial Analysis are examples of new technologies that are being used in digital humanities on the Semantic Web. These technologies have helped to democratize access to cultural and historical information, making it more widely available to scholars, students, and the general public. Furthermore, they have enabled new forms of interdisciplinary research and collaboration, generating insights that would not be possible using traditional methods alone.

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